

Book review: L. Woodrow (2022). *Introducing researching English for specific purposes*. Routledge.**Louise Kaktins¹***The University of Sydney*

Woodrow's *Introducing Researching English for Specific Purposes* is a comprehensive tome that explores key aspects of research into this increasingly significant branch of English language teaching. In the contemporary era, English is no longer a matter of acquiring another language; rather, it occupies a unique category among languages as an essential generic skill for career advancement (Kawsar, 2023). Under these circumstances, acquiring specialised English language knowledge streamlined for career advancement has far-reaching professional and economic consequences. Therefore, as an acknowledged expert in her discipline, Woodrow's contribution is a valuable and timely addition to the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) field by providing a seminal handbook for those wishing to undertake research in this area.

At the outset, a key area of focus in Woodrow's book is designing a research project (Chapter 2), including potential theoretical frameworks (Chapter 3) and researchable topics (Chapter 4). She initially focuses on the area of developing a research project (Chapter 2), explaining the typical stages leading to the writing of a research proposal. As she acknowledges, identifying and streamlining a suitable topic is often challenging for novice researchers; therefore, she includes extensive recommendations for suitable ESP research topics. The chapter highlights the criticality of reviewing the literature. She suggests four core stages to accomplish the latter: acquiring a basic knowledge of the area; reading widely to become familiar with key theories, notable scholars, current debates and seminal research papers; identifying a gap in the literature; and then writing the literature review. Importantly she also includes practical advice on ways to approach the task of

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reading the literature, which for academic purposes is notoriously voluminous and time-consuming. This chapter sets the pace for the rest of the book with the consistent inclusion of figures featuring authentic examples from dissertations and journal articles, to illustrate her explanations. This strategy becomes a defining feature of her book. Another is the inclusion of summary tables providing easy accessibility to key points in the chapter. Such figures and tables are interspersed throughout each chapter. For those wishing to immediately access or review specific examples, at the start of the book discrete tables of contents are provided for figures as well as tables.

Theoretical conceptualisations in ESP research (Chapter 3), discussed by Woodrow, include genre and intercultural perspectives, of which English as a lingua franca (ELF), as well as its offshoot, business English as a lingua franca (BELF), academic literacies theory, and critical perspectives. Of these, the first – genre theory – has enjoyed widespread popularity among ESP researchers, given that specific genres are core to teaching ESP. Here, Woodrow acknowledges the contribution of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) in setting the benchmark for much ESP research. Woodrow, next, groups intercultural perspectives with English as a lingua franca, business English as a lingua franca, and critical perspectives. Finally, she considers the academic literacies approach, aligned with English for Academic Purposes (EAP), specifically highlighting its application to tertiary study and the core skill of academic writing.

Considering Woodrow's focus on academic literacies in the previous chapter, it is unsurprising that she starts Chapter 4 (on potential research topics) with a close examination of English for Academic Purposes. In this chapter, she draws on authentic examples from two particularly highly regarded academic journals in the ESP/EAP area, namely *English for Specific Purposes* and the *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*. This way, she directs novices to high-quality research sources and encourages them to familiarise themselves with journals to which they may potentially submit articles in the future.

A sizable portion of the book—Chapters 5 through 8—is devoted to methodological approaches in ESP research, including extended chapters on quantitative (Chapter 6) and qualitative (Chapter 7) research.

To help novice researchers in their choice of appropriate methodology, Woodrow again complements her wider discussion with explicit tables to support such decision-making. For example, the suite of tables in Chapter 7 differentiates

between quantitative and qualitative research design (Table 7.1, p. 121) and highlights the advantages/disadvantages of qualitative research (Table 7.2, p.121). Earlier in Chapter 6, the advantages/disadvantages of quantitative research (Table 6.3, pp. 88-89) are presented. To complement, there are also examples of quantitative research questions (Table 6.1, p. 88) and qualitative research questions (Table 6.2, p. 88). If anything, this particular arrangement might have been streamlined for more cohesive progression such that Table 7.1 would have been better located in Chapter 5 which presents a general overview of ESP research design and Table 6.2 restricted to the chapter on qualitative research. This is a minor criticism in an otherwise finely-tuned compositional layout aligning with the target audience.

The section on methodology continues in Chapter 8, focusing on validity, reliability and ethics. Woodrow differentiates between what is accepted as reliability in quantitative research and validity in qualitative research. In Table 8.2 (p. 162), she classifies quantitative research as subject to internal and external reliability and internal, external and construct validity. In contrast, qualitative research is subject to dependability, credibility, transferability and confirmability. She then identifies and addresses the challenges to these standards (Table 8.3, pp. 164-165). This chapter also considers the ethical aspects permeating the entire research process. Woodrow deconstructs some general guidelines for ethical research (Table 8.4, p. 167) and some foci related to institutional ethics applications (Table 8.5, p.168). Her final recommendation is that researchers engage in self-reflexive practice, especially by keeping an ongoing research diary.

Chapter 9 entitled "Using research findings" provides a solid framework for structuring the final product – specifically a dissertation for a master's degree. The examples included in this chapter are taken from the British Council TESOL dissertation awards site, and hyperlinks are included should readers wish to access the full dissertations. Woodrow starts with a comparison of a dissertation and a journal article and how the purpose and content of sections are differentiated (pp. 174-175). She continues with detailed explanations of the key dissertation sections – introduction, literature review, methodology, results, discussion, and conclusion – supported by the ever-present authentic exemplars and summary tables.

The final chapter (Chapter 10) directs readers to wide-ranging resources for developing and conducting ESP research including reliable academic journals, handbooks, data analysis software packages, and useful corpora. There is a suite of

Appendices featuring examples of associated official documentation that students will encounter during their research journey, such as a Participant Consent Form (p. 222), followed by a Glossary (pp. 227-233).

Other more current publications concerned with methodologies and research have done so partially with a broader focus on ESP, such as Belcher, Johns and Paltridge (2011) and Paltridge and Starfield (2013). Coxhead (2017), while devoting her entire book to quantitative and qualitative ESP perspectives, has done so with an exclusive focus on specialised vocabulary. Woodrow's book complements these earlier publications and adds a further dimension by providing an extremely comprehensive, in-depth, research-dedicated stand-alone ESP tome that will not only please experts in the field but is predicted to prove an invaluable resource for novice researchers, such as new postgraduates, who can continue revisiting this work at different stages as their research trajectory warrants. Those students who are fledging researchers at the start of their research journey will most benefit from Woodrow's work as she deconstructs and demystifies the multifaceted world of research in general and ESP research in particular.

Her meticulous sequential arrangement of the book and her explicit efforts to break down the more esoteric aspects will facilitate students' transition from research interns to confident independent researchers. This is a timely publication in an era when research is becoming a benchmark for professional development and academic promotion. While ESP practitioners would be the primary beneficiaries, it is evident that much of the book can similarly be utilised more universally as a seminal framework for undertaking research in various other disciplines.

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